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Whispers of the Originals

Along the Cordillera mountains,
Where clouds conceal emerald heights,
The terraces rise like old stairways,
Tales held through many a night.
The stones recollect every step,
Of wise and mighty sires;
Who shaped the mountains with slow hands,
Under the sun and in the highland sky.

In the valleys the hudhud calls out,
Its melodies floated on the wind;
Stories of bravery and kinship
Of where our folk always have been.
The forests sigh through the muyong,
The rivers sing their song of old,
Lessons of care and balance taught,
Which have led the people all the way.

But change comes on the mountains,
As the day changes with roads and screens,
Many youngsters leave the playgrounds of their fathers
And old traditions fade away slow.
But the rice terraces still stand,
Their beauty is written on every hill;
A living monument of a race
Whose heart is stout and true.

Silence is not the language of the ancestors,
But under the earth beneath our feet;
In each harvest, chant, assembly,
Our future responds to their wisdom.
More than a responsibility to save these mountains,
It's to honor who we've been;
To keep alive the language and the stories;
Passed down like the light of a far-off star.

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Let us then listen to their whispers,
Out of our highland's morning mist;
So long as the terraces are there
The spirit of Ifugao lives on.
And when future generations walk
Free and high, among the mountains,
May they hear the voices of their forebears
In every stone and tree and rice terrace they see